

The Value and Values of Openness: Open Source, AI Openness, and the Future of Digital Public Goods

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Abstract

Openness has emerged as a central paradigm in digital innovation, shaping software, artificial intelligence (AI), and the wider digital economy. This paper explores the multifaceted concept of openness as both a philosophical and practical framework for innovation, governance, and value creation. Drawing on evidence from OpenUK's State of Open and AI Openness reports (2021–2025), and integrating recent academic and policy research, it argues that openness functions simultaneously as an economic multiplier, a mechanism for digital sovereignty, and an ethical model for public-interest technology. The paper situates open source software and AI openness within the broader discourse on digital public goods, highlighting their contribution to sustainable growth, resilience, and societal trust. It concludes that, as nations seek to balance competitiveness with accountability, open approaches to AI and software governance represent both a moral imperative and a strategic advantage for the United Kingdom and the global community.

Introduction

The principle of openness has shaped the evolution of digital technology for more than four decades, serving as a cornerstone of the software ecosystem as we know it today. Over this time, the concept of open collaboration has redefined the creation and exchange of knowledge, infrastructure, and innovation (Weber, 2004; Benkler, 2006). Today, as artificial intelligence (AI) systems transform economies and societies, openness once again stands at a pivotal crossroads.

This paper argues that we must move beyond technical admiration or economic convenience and begin to truly value openness, recognising both its measurable economic impact and its deeper societal values. We explore how open source contributes to digital sovereignty, productivity, and innovation, and why their recognition as public goods is essential for responsible regulation, funding, and standards development.

The case argument for openness rests on three interconnected foundations: economic value, sovereignty and security, and trust and transparency. From an economic standpoint, open source practices encourage reuse, interoperability, and innovation at scale, reducing duplication of effort and nurturing vibrant ecosystems (Hoffmann, Nagle, & Zhou, 2024). In terms of sovereignty, open technologies enable nations and organisations to retain control over critical digital infrastructure, reducing dependence on proprietary vendors and foreign supply chains. Ethically, openness aligns with the democratic principles of accountability, inclusion, and the right to inspect and improve technologies, especially those that are increasingly governing human lives (OECD, 2023).

Open source occupies a unique position, sitting where value meets values. It is at once a vast infrastructure supporting the digital economy and a distinctive ethical–political formation. Its economic significance is widely acknowledged: open source software forms the foundation of nearly all digital systems, fuelling innovation, interoperability, and market growth. Yet its resilience depends equally on a shared cultural economy — the practices of openness, reciprocity, and collaborative maintenance that allow these systems to flourish. To appreciate this duality, open source must be seen not just as a production model but as a relational ecology in which economic value and ethical values continually reinforce one another.

Michel Serres’s philosophy of communication and relation suggests that exchange, mediation and translation displace traditional hierarchies of subject and object. Serres (1980; 1990) conceptualises social and material systems as topological rather than linear — as dynamic networks of flows and relations in which each entity simultaneously hosts and is hosted by others. This paper follows a “trail of associations between seemingly heterogeneous elements” where there might be something formed anew. One follows assemblages topologically (rather than cartographically), seeking the places and moments where things gather and how and where they connect to other gatherings. Topology, in Serres’ terms, is the science of nearness and rifts; gatherings or folds, as he calls them, are made of “multiple pleats” (Serres and Latour, 1995: 60).

Value, understood in this way, is never static or proprietary: it emerges through the circulation of information, energy, people and meaning within a network of relations. Open source exemplifies this topology. Its productivity stems from sharing, reuse, and iterative modification - what Serres might describe as the transformation of the “noise” of collective communication into the “signal” of functional code and communities. Like Serres’s host–parasite relation, the open source commons relies on constant renegotiation between giving and taking, use and contribution. It is a dynamic ecology of dependencies. Viewed through this lens, open source shows that value — economic, technical, or social — is inseparable from the values that organise the relations of exchange. Trust, transparency, and reciprocity are not byproducts but conditions of production.

The Economic Value for Openness

The economic case for openness has evolved from a narrow technical argument about software efficiency to a broader macroeconomic framework for sustainable innovation. Today, open source ecosystems underpin the vast majority of the global digital economy – in fact, estimates suggest that “Open source components now account for up to 90% of modern software applications”. Harvard Business School’s 2024 working paper *The Value of Open Source* estimates that open source contributes around USD 8 trillion annually to global economic activity, reflecting the combined value of shared intellectual property, collaborative R&D, and the multiplier effects of reusable code (Hoffmann, M., Nagle, F., & Zhou, Y., 2024) Unfortunately this research is unreproducible as it relies on closed data for its analysis.

OpenUK’s *State of Open* series provides empirical evidence that illustrates how these dynamics play out within the United Kingdom. In *Phase Three: The Values of Open* (2021), open source

was estimated to contribute between £43.15 billion and £46.5 billion annually to the UK economy through direct productivity gains, cost savings, and innovation spillovers (OpenUK, 2021). By 2023, the UK had become one of the top five global contributors to open source software, accounting for about 5% of all GitHub repositories worldwide and ranking first in Europe (OpenUK, 2023).

The 2023 *Phase Two* OpenUK report estimated that open source software contributes £13.59 billion in gross value added (GVA) to the UK economy, based on developer activity and sectoral integration. This is about 27% of the UK tech sector GVA from open source software. While significant, this figure remains conservative, limited by data limitations and the constraints of existing modelling approaches.

What remains missing is a paradigm shift: a move from treating open source as a cost saving tool to recognising it as a productive force—one that drives innovation, efficiency, and resilience. Open source reduces duplication, accelerates development cycles, and enables interoperability across sectors. It allows public institutions to build infrastructure free from vendor lock-in and the ability to collaborate made more fluid and empowers private companies to scale rapidly.

The impact of openness extends well beyond the software industry. Open innovation is accelerating digitalisation across sectors such as finance, healthcare, and energy. When public sector procurement aligns with open technologies, it becomes a powerful economic lever. In the UK, where public procurement accounts for roughly 16% of GDP, mandating open standards and open source solutions across government infrastructure could amplify competition, reduce vendor lock-in, and create significant multiplier effects throughout the digital economy (OpenUK, 2024a; OECD, 2021).

Investment in open source, data, and AI skills also fuels a self-reinforcing growth loop: skills investment boosts participation in open ecosystems, which in turn drives innovation and economic resilience (OpenUK, 2024b). This dynamic aligns with the theory of “knowledge spillovers” in innovation economics (Romer, 1990; von Hippel, 2005), in which freely shared resources generate exponential returns for societies rather than linear profits for individual firms.

A 2023 OECD analysis found a positive correlation between open source adoption, national digital competitiveness indices and total factor productivity (OECD, 2023). Countries that invest in open infrastructure see higher innovation outputs per R&D dollar, largely because open collaboration reduces duplication of research and accelerates time-to-market. However, researchers continue to face funding challenges that limit their ability to sustain robust open source communities and tools.

Major UK enterprises such as the BBC, Skyscanner, and Nationwide Building Society attribute their agility, security, and long-term cost efficiency to open source strategies (OpenUK, 2022). Beyond cost savings, open collaboration fosters a culture of experimentation and transparency that attracts technical talent and aligns with corporate sustainability goals.

From an economic perspective, open source ecosystems simultaneously reduce frictional costs by enabling shared innovation and create competitive advantage through community-driven improvement. As markets transition toward AI-enabled systems, these same principles apply to open AI models — where shared datasets, weights, and architectures can lower barriers to entry, diversify participation, and stimulate localised innovation.

Countries that invest in AI openness are already seeing significant growth across related digital sectors. India’s open AI repository base grew by 38 per cent year-on-year, France by 26 per cent, while the UK maintained European leadership in total repository count (OpenUK, 2025). These trends indicate that openness not only enhances economic competitiveness, but also promotes inclusivity and ethical engagement.

Ultimately, the economic value of openness lies in its ability to reshape the innovation economy from a proprietary race for advantage into a cooperative system of shared progress. By transforming software, AI, and data into digital public goods (UNDP, 2023), open ecosystems foster collective resilience and distribute economic gains more equitably across society.

To properly value the economy of open source, we must look beyond traditional models of total cost of production or labour data. We need broader definitions of what kinds of relations and productivity create value and economic impact. Determining what to include in such valuation is difficult – it raises the usual questions of how to value intangibles in a vibrant economic system. This paper considers some of the factors that need to be accounted for in that evolving framework.

Sovereignty & Security

In this digital age, sovereignty is increasingly defined not by territorial borders but by control over infrastructure, data, and technological capability. Digital sovereignty — a state’s ability to develop, maintain, and govern its digital systems independently — has become a central theme in both national and international policy discourse (European Commission, 2023). Within this context, openness offers a paradoxical yet powerful model: by enabling shared access to code, standards, and data, open ecosystems enhance resilience and reduce dependence on external monopolies.

Open source strengthens digital sovereignty through transparency, interoperability, and control (OpenUK, 2024a). Proprietary systems, while sometimes offering short term efficiency, create long term dependencies that lock users and governments into closed architectures and supply chains. By contrast, open source ecosystems can be audited, modified, and maintained locally, ensuring continuity of essential services and fostering self-reliance. This approach aligns with the UK Government’s *Digital Data and Technology Playbook* (Cabinet Office, 2021), which identifies open standards as the foundation of secure, sustainable digital infrastructure.

In this light, then, openness can be understood as a model of “sovereign stewardship” of technology — one that balances collaboration and control (OpenUK, 2025). This form of stewardship encourages nations to participate in shared innovation while retaining agency over their own implementations. This argument has become particularly relevant amid the global

debate on AI regulation, where geopolitical tensions between the United States and China have transformed openness itself into a strategic issue. For example, the release of China's *DeepSeek R1* reasoning model — trained through open reinforcement learning and released under an MIT licence — illustrates how open AI can disrupt existing geopolitical hierarchies while also raising critical questions about data governance and security (OpenUK, 2025).

From a policy perspective, the European Union's approach to digital sovereignty demonstrates both the promise and the challenge of openness. The EU's *Open Source Software Strategy 2020-2023* and *AI Act* (adopted 2024) recognise that open source can advance technological independence while supporting regulatory oversight (European Commission, 2024). By mandating transparency in algorithms and data, these frameworks position openness as a prerequisite for trust in AI systems. Yet, as Harvard's Ben Brooks noted in conversation with OpenUK, the same openness that empowers developers can expose vulnerabilities if not matched with robust security and identity protocols (OpenUK, 2025).

Security, therefore, should be understood not as a counterpoint to openness but as one of its core outcomes. One might identify curation, maintenance, and community governance as the pillars of "trustworthy open source" (OpenUK, 2022). These practices — supported by clear licensing, timely security patching, and software bill-of-materials (SBOM) standards — ensures that open codebases can meet or even exceed proprietary benchmarks for resilience. Global initiatives such as the *Open Source Security Foundation (OpenSSF)* and the *U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) AI Risk Management Framework (2023)* further reinforces the idea that security is a shared responsibility within open ecosystems.

The UK provides compelling examples of how openness can serve as a strategic enabler of national security and autonomy. Projects like the *Open Energy Programme* and the NHS's adoption of open electronic health record standards have improved interoperability and transparency in critical national systems. Public sector institutions that embrace open infrastructure gain not only technical flexibility but also long term independence from single vendors. This autonomy is increasingly crucial in the AI domain, where model weights, training data, and computational resources are increasingly controlled by a handful of global corporations.

Finally, openness supports what the OECD (2023) terms "resilient interdependence" — the ability of nations to collaborate internationally without relinquishing sovereignty. Rather than promoting isolation, openness enables countries to pool knowledge, resources, and technical capacity while maintaining local governance over how those technologies are implemented and used. As the global AI ecosystem becomes ever more interlinked, maintaining this balance between cooperation and control will define the next decade of digital policy.

AI, and the Future of Innovation

Historically, "open source software" has referred to transparent, modifiable software codebases. Yet with the rapid rise of AI, the concept of openness now extends beyond code to include data, model weights, and algorithmic architectures. This broader notion of AI openness reflects the

reality that AI systems are built upon vast, interdependent ecosystems of software, hardware, and data infrastructure (OpenUK, 2025).

Recent work highlights a conceptual shift from “open source AI” toward “AI openness” and “public good AI.” This evolution reflects a growing recognition that the debate is no longer only about technical accessibility, but about ethical and societal purpose. This reframing positions openness as essential for building trust, ensuring transparency, and democratising participation in AI development and governance (OpenUK, 2025).

Three interlinked dimensions capture the essence of AI openness: iterative innovation, democratisation of access, and trust through transparency. Iterative innovation builds on the open source principle of “standing on the shoulders of giants”, where each innovation becomes the foundation for the next (OpenUK, 2025). The development of China’s *DeepSeek R1* reasoning model, trained using distilled open models such as Meta’s *LLaMA* and *Qwen*, exemplifies this recursive process of innovation. Democratisation of access ensures that individuals, small enterprises, and researchers can meaningfully engage in AI development without prohibitive costs. Finally, transparency enables the inspection of data sources, algorithms, and decision making processes, a precondition for accountability in both public and private sectors.

These principles are increasingly reflected in global policy. The OECD’s *AI Principles* (2023) and UNESCO’s *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence* (2022) both emphasise transparency, accountability, and inclusivity as foundations for trustworthy AI. The UK’s Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT) has echoed this approach through its AI Security Institute (AISI) and its open source Inspect platform, which enables the testing and validation of AI models in collaboration with international partners (OpenUK, 2024a). The AISI’s open methodology demonstrates a practical application of openness as a governance mechanism, embedding accountability directly into the tools used to assess risk and safety. That the AISI started as the ‘AI Safety Institute’ and has now changed ‘Safety’ to ‘Security’ points to a broader political and global economic positioning for the UK in the AI space.

At the same time, the tension between open and closed approaches to AI remains unresolved. Advocates for closed source models argue that openness can expose systems to misuse or exploitation, particularly in sensitive domains such as national security or healthcare (Brundage et al., 2020). Yet the alternative — concentrating AI capabilities within a small number of opaque corporate entities — risks far greater harm by eroding public trust and undermining competition. As Ben Brooks of Harvard’s Berkman Klein Center observed in the *AI Openness Update* (OpenUK, 2025), the question is no longer whether openness should exist but how it should be governed. Regulation must encourage transparency without stifling innovation, striking a balance between safety and participation.

The emergence of agentic AI — autonomous systems capable of independent reasoning and goal setting — makes this balance even more urgent. As Toren Bruce Richards, creator of AutoGPT, notes, restricting access to open agents “removes the fundamental value they bring” (OpenUK, 2025, p. 28). When governed transparently, agentic systems could democratise productivity by automating routine tasks and enabling individuals and small organisations to

compete with large-scale enterprises. Without openness, however, these same systems risk concentrating power further within closed, proprietary ecosystems.

OpenUK's 2024 and 2025 analyses suggest that the UK is well positioned to lead globally in AI innovation. The nation ranks third worldwide in open AI repository count and first in Europe by total volume of AI repositories hosted on GitHub and Hugging Face (OpenUK, 2025). Still, competition is growing: both India and France have adopted pro-open source policies, positioning openness as a driver of digital sovereignty and economic growth (Government of India, 2024; Government de la France, 2024). These processes need to be supported as a global initiative.

This shift raises the question: what does this mean for values? Floridi (2023) and Whittlestone (2022) argue that AI openness aligns with the principles of responsible innovation — innovation that is reflexive, inclusive, and guided by ethical foresight. Openness allows diverse stakeholders to audit, challenge, and improve AI systems collectively, creating a shared framework for progress that reflect societal values rather than solely commercial incentives.

The emerging concept of public good AI encapsulates this vision. Public good AI treats openness not just as a technical or operational feature but as both an ethical and economic imperative. In this paradigm, AI systems are developed as part of a digital commons — shared resources governed through transparent, inclusive, and accountable processes. As the global AI landscape matures, this framework may well determine whether AI serves humanity collectively or consolidates benefit within a few powerful hands.

Ethics, Trust, and Public Goods

The shift from proprietary control to openness represents not only a technological transformation but also an ethical reorientation — one that reframes innovation as a collective good rather than a private asset. Open approaches to software, data, and AI distribute both the power and the responsibility of digital creation across society, forming the basis for a new social contract for the digital age (Stilgoe, 2020; OpenUK, 2025).

Trust in technology depends fundamentally on transparency. Curation, maintenance, and accountability are key to ensuring “trustworthy open source” (OpenUK, 2022). Openness enables visibility not only in the code itself but also in how projects are governed and decisions are made. This allows communities to collectively inspect, verify, and improve technologies. In this sense, openness operationalises values, making fairness, accountability, and inclusivity technically possible.

The link between openness and public trust has now been embedded in major international frameworks. The OECD's *Principles on Artificial Intelligence* (2023) call for AI systems that are transparent, accountable, and human-centred. Similarly, the EU's *AI Act* (2024) establishes requirements for explainability and documentation of high-risk AI systems, while UNESCO's *Recommendation on the Ethics of AI* (2022) promotes collective benefit and human rights as core guiding values. Together, these frameworks converge on the idea that openness (whether in datasets, algorithms, or governance) is essential to legitimacy and public confidence in AI (Floridi, 2023; Brundage et al., 2020).

The ecosystem of open collaboration creates what might be called a distributed ethics, in which responsibility is collectively held and continually enacted. This approach aligns with the framework of responsible innovation, which integrates anticipation, inclusion, reflexivity, and responsiveness into the design and deployment of technology (Stilgoe et al., 2013).

Here, Michel Serres's concept of a *topology of relations* offers a useful metaphor. In such a network, meaning, value, and responsibility circulate through continual exchange. Ethics, in this view, is not imposed from above but emerges from within: a form of *distributed ethics* where responsibility is collectively held and continuously enacted. While in practice very little is so perfectly aligned or delivered, Serres reminds us that communication always entails transformation: the "noise" of multiple voices is not disorder but the very medium through which new forms of order arise. Openness, therefore, enables a form of responsible innovation that integrates anticipation, inclusion, reflexivity, and responsiveness into the fabric of technological practice (Stilgoe et al., 2013). Responsibility may, then, be better understood as relational rather than purely regulatory, although the impact of the narrative on regulation cannot be underestimated.

Perhaps a more concrete way to imagine this is by considering open source as digital public good. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2023) defines digital public goods as open source software, open data, open AI models, and open content that advance the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By this definition, open technologies — and increasingly AI that is open — represent shared infrastructure for global progress. They can expand equitable access to digital capabilities, empower local innovation, and reduce duplication of investment across borders.

Open source also allows governments to reframe digital investments as contributions to a collective commons rather than as isolated expenditures (OpenUK, 2024a). When public funds are used to develop digital technologies, openness ensures that the resulting outputs — from data platforms to AI safety tools — can be reused, adapted, and built upon globally. This principle underpins the growing movement for "public money, public code" now embraced by multiple governments and international organisations (Free Software Foundation Europe, 2023).

The ethical imperative of openness also extends to equity and inclusion. Closed digital ecosystems often reproduce existing social inequalities by restricting access to tools, data, and computational resources. Open ecosystems, by contrast, enable participation from a wider diversity of contributors, including underrepresented communities, researchers in the Global South, and small enterprises. Training and skills developed through open collaboration often transcend borders, bringing even the most isolated into international employment and learning opportunities.

Of course, the challenge is not without complexity. The question of how to balance the benefits of openness with the need for responsible oversight is currently in hot debate. There is a pressing need for technical standards, legal clarity, and community standards that uphold privacy, security, and fairness.

Ultimately, the trustworthiness of digital technologies depends on whether their governance aligns with public values. Open ecosystems create opportunities for citizens to participate

directly in shaping the digital infrastructure that affects their daily lives. In doing so, they bridge the gap between innovation and accountability. By framing openness as both an ethical commitment and a structural necessity — combining the values and the value — policymakers and technologists can cultivate a digital future grounded in human dignity, transparency, and shared prosperity.

Policy and the Path Ahead

The future of openness as a guiding principle in digital governance depends on the ability of policymakers to convert ideals into institutional practice. The UK's global leadership in open source must be supported through coherent, cross-sector policy frameworks that link skills, procurement, innovation, and regulation. In this vision, openness is not a single policy objective but a foundational infrastructure for the digital economy — one that requires long term investment in people, standards, and public trust.

1. Building Skills and Capacity

OpenUK's reports from 2023 through 2025 consistently identify a skills gap as a structural barrier to open innovation. The UK's open source workforce represents a vast but often invisible network of developers, data scientists, and engineers whose contributions underpin national productivity (OpenUK, 2024b). These technical contributors are supported by organisational, administrative, and business leaders who help translate open collaboration into real world impact. Embedding open source competencies into national curricula, apprenticeship schemes, and public sector training programmes would help address the digital skills shortage while democratising access to high value technology careers. This approach aligns with OECD recommendations (2023), which advocate for “open skills ecosystems” to ensure inclusive participation in the AI-driven economy.

2. Public Sector Leadership

Public procurement remains the most powerful policy lever for embedding openness into digital practice. As Iain Mitchell KC (2024) notes, procurement accounts for more than 16% of UK GDP — a scale that can reshape markets when directed toward open standards and technologies. The UK's *Digital Data and Technology Playbook* (Cabinet Office, 2021) already recognises the importance of open standards, but implementation remains uneven across departments. OpenUK (2024a) recommends creating a central “Open Technology Office” to coordinate standards, compliance, and capacity across government departments. Such a body could mirror the success of the U.S. and EU *Open Source Program Offices* (OSPOs), ensuring consistent governance and accountability for open digital projects. By institutionalising open practices within public procurement, the government can lead by example and create ripple effects across the private sector.

3. AI Openness and Safety

As AI systems increasingly influence public and economic life, ensuring that they operate transparently and safely is paramount. The establishment of the UK's AI Security Institute (AISI)

in 2023 demonstrates how openness can coexist with rigorous oversight. The Institute’s open source Inspect platform enables independent testing of large language models for safety, bias, and robustness — a practice that could become an international standard. (OpenUK, 2024a). By embedding open methodologies into AI governance, the UK can take a leading role in international efforts to align AI innovation with ethical and societal values in line with OECD and UNESCO frameworks (OECD, 2023; UNESCO, 2022). This approach would also support the UK’s ambition to position itself as a global hub for safe and trustworthy AI.

4. International Collaboration and Digital Sovereignty

As the *OpenUK AI Openness Update (2025)* highlights, openness has become a geopolitical concern. Global AI summits — including Bletchley Park (2023), Seoul (2024), and Paris (2025) — have all positioned openness as central to responsible AI governance. France’s emphasis on “public interest AI” and India’s commitment to “access for all” through open AI ecosystems signal a growing international consensus: collaboration, not competition, will define technological sovereignty (OpenUK, 2025).

For the UK, proactive participation in these frameworks — particularly through the G7 and OECD — offers a strategic opportunity to shape international norms around openness, transparency, and interoperability. Engagement at this level can also strengthen alliances and ensure that the UK’s leadership in open innovation translates into influence within global governance.

5. Institutionalising Openness

For openness to endure, it must be embedded into institutions, through law, policy, and culture. This requires a whole-of-government approach that treats openness as the default, not the exception. The European Commission’s *Open Source Strategy (2023)* and the UNDP’s *Digital Public Goods Alliance (2023)* provide models for integrating openness across national strategies. Domestically, OpenUK recommends integrating open technology goals into the UK’s Industrial Strategy, explicitly linking them to priorities such as net zero, digital inclusion, and AI safety (OpenUK, 2024a). Such alignment would reinforce openness not just as a public value but as a measurable contributor to economic growth, social equity, and environmental sustainability.

Conclusion

Openness has moved from the margins of digital policy to its centre — a defining paradigm for economic growth, ethical governance, and technological sovereignty. Evidence from OpenUK’s longitudinal research, alongside global academic and policy institutions, points to a consistent conclusion: openness delivers measurable economic value, strengthens trust, and ensures resilience in a volatile technological landscape.

For the United Kingdom, embedding openness into the fabric of digital governance represents both a strategic opportunity and a moral responsibility. By advancing open source software, open AI, and open data as digital public goods, the UK can lead a global transition toward a more transparent, equitable, and sustainable digital future.

The challenge now lies in execution — in turning the principles of openness into the default practice of digital life.

References

Benkler, Y. (2006). *The wealth of networks: How social production transforms markets and freedom*. Yale University Press. https://www.benkler.org/Benkler_Wealth_Of_Networks.pdf

Brundage, M., Avin, S., Wang, J., Belfield, H., Krueger, G., Hadfield, G., ... & Anderljung, M. (2020). *Toward trustworthy AI development: Mechanisms for supporting verifiable claims*. Centre for the Governance of AI, Future of Humanity Institute, University of Oxford. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2004.07213>

Cabinet Office. (2023). *The digital, data and technology playbook: Transforming public procurement*. Government of the United Kingdom, June 2023. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-digital-data-and-technology-playbook/the-digital-data-and-technology-playbook>

European Commission. (2023). *Open source software strategy 2020–2023*. Publications Office of the European Union. https://commission.europa.eu/about/departments-and-executive-agencies/digital-services/open-source-software-strategy_en

European Commission. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence Act: Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council*. Official Journal of the European Union.

Floridi, L. (2023). *The ethics of artificial intelligence: Principles, challenges, and opportunities*. Oxford University Press.

Free Software Foundation Europe. (2023). *Public money, public code: Policy brief*. FSFE. Found online: <https://fsfe.org/activities/publiccode/publiccode.en.html>

Government of India. (2024). *National strategy for artificial intelligence 2024: Responsible and inclusive AI for all*. Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology.

Gouvernement de la France. (2024). *Stratégie nationale pour l'intelligence artificielle, phase 2: IA ouverte et d'intérêt public*. Secrétariat d'État au Numérique.

Hoffmann, M., Nagle, F., & Zhou, Y. (2024). *The value of open source*. Harvard Business School Working Paper 24-038. https://www.hbs.edu/ris/Publication%20Files/24-038_51f8444f-502c-4139-8bf2-56eb4b65c58a.pdf

Mitchell, I. (2024). *Shaping markets through public procurement*. In *State of Open: The UK in 2024, Phase Three – Open Source and Market Shaping* (pp. 23–37). OpenUK.

OpenUK. (2021). *State of Open: The UK in 2021, Phase Three – The Values of Open*. London: OpenUK. <https://openuk.uk/stateofopen/state-of-open-the-uk-in-2021-phase-3/>

OpenUK. (2022). *State of Open: The UK in 2022, Phase One – The Open Source Journey*. London: OpenUK. <https://openuk.uk/stateofopen/state-of-open-the-uk-in-2022/>

OpenUK. (2023). *State of Open: The UK in 2023, Phase Two – Show Us the Money: The Economics of Open Source*. London: OpenUK. <https://openuk.uk/stateofopen/state-of-open-the-uk-in-2023-phase-2-part-1/>

OpenUK. (2024a). State of Open: The UK in 2024, Phase Three – Open Source and Market Shaping. London: OpenUK. <https://openuk.uk/stateofopen/stateofopentheukin2024-phase3/>

OpenUK. (2024b). State of Open: The UK in 2024, Phase Two – The Open Manifesto Report. London: OpenUK. <https://openuk.uk/stateofopen/state-of-open-the-uk-in-2024-phase-2-the-open-manifesto/>

OpenUK. (2025). AI Openness Update: From Agentic to Public Good. London: OpenUK. <https://openuk.uk/stateofopen/publicgoodai/>

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2021). Public procurement for innovation: Lessons from country experiences. OECD Publishing.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2023). OECD principles on artificial intelligence. OECD Publishing. Found online at <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/sub-issues/ai-principles.html>

Romer, P. (1990). Endogenous technological change. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5, Part 2), S71–S102. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2937632>

Stilgoe, J. (2020). *Who's driving innovation? New technologies and the collaborative state*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Stilgoe, J., Owen, R., & Macnaghten, P. (2013). Developing a framework for responsible innovation. *Research Policy*, 42(9), 1568–1580. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048733313000930>

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2023). *Digital public goods charter: Leveraging open digital infrastructure for sustainable development*. UNDP.

UNESCO. (2022). *Recommendation on the ethics of artificial intelligence*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

von Hippel, E. (2005). *Democratizing innovation*. MIT Press.

Weber, S. (2004). *The success of open source*. Harvard University Press.